

Type Theory based on Dependent Inductive and Coinductive Types

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Overview of the Talk

In this talk, we will develop a type theory that is based solely on dependent inductive and coinductive types. By this we mean that the only way to form new types is by specifying the type of their corresponding constructors or destructors, respectively. From such a specification, we get the corresponding recursion and corecursion principles. One might be tempted to think that such a theory is relatively weak as, for example, there is no function space type. However, as it turns out, the function space is definable as a coinductive type. In fact, we can encode the connectives of intuitionistic predicate logic: falsity, conjunction, disjunction, dependent function space, existential quantification, and equality. Further, well-known types like natural numbers, vectors etc. arise as well. The presented type theory is based on ideas from categorical logic that have been investigated before by the first author, and it extends Hagino's categorical data types to a dependently typed setting. By basing the type theory on concepts from category theory we maintain the duality between inductive and coinductive types.

The reduction relation on terms consists solely of a rule for recursion and a rule for corecursion. We can then derive the usual computation rules for encoded types these basic rules. This results in a type theory with a small set of rules, while still being fairly expressive. To further support the introduction of this new type theory, we prove subject reduction and strong normalisation of the reduction relation.

Why do we need another type theory, especially since Martin-Löf type theory (MLTT) or the calculus of inductive constructions (CoIC) are well-studied frameworks for intuitionistic logic? The main reason is that the existing type theories have no explicit dependent coinductive types. There is support for them in implementations like Coq, based on early ideas by Giménez, and Agda. However, both have no formal justification, and Coq's coinductive types are known to have problems (e.g. related to subject reduction). The calculus of constructions has been extended with streams in such a way that Coq's problems do not arise, but the problem of limited support remains. Just as Sacchini's work can be seen as formal justification of (parts of) Coq, the type theory we study here can be seen as formal justification for (an extension of) Agda's coinductive types.

One might argue that dependent coinductive types can be encoded through inductive types. However, it is not clear whether such an encoding gives rise to a good computation principle in an intensional type theory such as MLTT or CoIC. This becomes an issue once we try to prove propositions about terms of coinductive type.

Other reasons for considering a new type theory are of foundational interest. First, taking inductive and coinductive types as core of the type theory reduces the number of deduction rules considerably. For each type former one needs the corresponding type rule, and introduction and elimination rules. This makes for a considerable amount of rules in MLTT with W- and M-types, while our theory only has 6 relevant deduction rules. Second, it is an interesting fact that the (dependent) function space can be described as a coinductive type. This seems to be

widely accepted but we do not know of any formal treatment of this fact. Thus the presented type theory allows us to deepen our understanding of coinductive types.

Contributions Having discussed the *raison d'être* of this work, let us briefly mention the technical contributions. First of all, we introduce the type theory and show how important logical operators can be represented in it. We also discuss some other basic examples, including one that shows the difference to existing theories with coinductive types. Second, we show that computations of terms, given in form of a reduction relation, are meaningful, in the sense that the reduction relation preserves types (subject reduction) and that all computations are terminating (strong normalisation). Thus, under the propositions-as-types interpretation, our type theory can serve as formal framework for intuitionistic reasoning.

Related Work A major source of inspiration for the setup of our type theory is categorical logic. Especially, the use of fibrations helped a great deal in understanding how coinductive types should be treated. Another source of inspiration is the view of type theories as internal language or even free model for categories. This view is especially important in topos theory, where final coalgebras have been used as foundation for predicative, constructive set theory.

Let us briefly discuss other type theories that the present work relates to. Especially close is the copattern calculus, as there the coinductive types are also specified by the types of their destructors. However, said calculus does not have dependent types, and it is based on systems of equations to define terms, whereas the calculus in the present work is based on recursion and corecursion schemes.

To ensure strong normalisation, the copatterns have been combined with size annotations. Due to the nature of the reduction relation in these copattern-based calculi, strong normalisation also ensure productivity for coinductive types or, more generally, well-definedness. As another way to ensure productivity, guarded recursive types have been proposed and guarded recursion has been extended to dependent types. Guarded recursive types are not only applicable to strictly positive types, which we restrict to here, but also to positive and even negative types. However, it is not clear how one can include inductive types into such a type theory, which are, in the authors opinion, crucial to mathematics and computer science.

Sneak Preview

Let us briefly peek at the calculus we are going to see in the talk. An important type formation rule is that for coinductive types:

$$\frac{k = 1, \dots, n \quad \sigma_k : \Gamma_k \triangleright \Gamma \quad \Theta, X : \Gamma \rightarrow * \mid \Gamma_k \vdash A_k : *}{\Theta \mid \emptyset \vdash \nu(X : \Gamma \rightarrow *; \vec{\sigma}; \vec{A}) : \Gamma \rightarrow *}$$

Here, n is a positive natural number and each σ_k is a substitution for the variables of the context Γ by terms in context Γ_k . The notation $X : \Gamma \rightarrow *$ indicates a type constructor variable that can be instantiated with terms according to Γ . The judgement $\Theta, X : \Gamma \rightarrow * \mid \Gamma_k \vdash A_k : *$ then says that each A_k is a type with free type constructor variables in Θ extended with X , and free term variables in Γ_k . The intuition is that $\nu(X : \Gamma \rightarrow *; \vec{\sigma}; \vec{A})$ has destructors that can only be applied to elements of this type instantiated with terms that match with σ_k and with output of type $A_k[\nu/X]$. These destructors are formally terms for each $k = 1, \dots, n$

$$\xi_k : (\Gamma_k, x : \nu @ \sigma_k) \rightarrow A_k[\nu/X],$$

where $\nu @ \sigma_k$ denotes the instantiation of the type with terms in σ_k .